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Optimising UHMWPE/BaTiO₃ Nanocomposites for Biomedical Applications: Role of Surface Functionalisation in Enhancing Performance

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Abstract. The advancement of sophisticated polymer nanocomposites for load-bearing orthopedic implants necessitates remarkable mechanical strength, wear resistance, and biocompatibility [1]. This study focuses on the reinforcement of ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) with barium titanate (BaTiO₃) nanoparticles, aiming to produce nanocomposites that exhibit amended performance characteristics. The fabrication process employed solvent dispersion, followed by compression moulding. A comprehensive evaluation was performed, which integrated mechanical testing, tribological analysis, and wettability assessment, in addition to further characterisations. After the initial performance, the composites were optimised through the functionalisation of BaTiO₃ with a silane coupling agent to enhance interfacial adhesion between the polymer matrix and the filler [2]. The effects of this functionalisation were gauged through mechanical and tribological characterisations. Additionally, bioactivity tests were performed by immersing the composites in simulated body fluid to assess their ability to form hydroxyapatite.

The study demonstrated that unfunctionalized nanocomposites possess advantageous tribological properties. Surface functionalisation resulted in improved mechanical properties and wear resistance when compared to the unfunctionalized composites. This research highlights the potential of both unfunctionalized and functionalised UHMWPE/BaTiO₃ nanocomposites for load-bearing implant applications, emphasising the considerable performance benefits achieved through surface functionalisation.

1. Introduction

Ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) is extensively utilised in high-performance applications, including orthopedic implants and wear-resistant components, due to its remarkable wear resistance, biocompatibility, and low friction characteristics. To further improve its properties, this work is focused on nanocomposite fabrications, particularly through the incorporation of ceramic nanofillers [3,4].

Barium titanate (BaTiO_3), a piezoelectric perovskite oxide, has shown significant promise as a functional filler in various applications. It has been chosen as a filler for fabricated UHMWPE nanocomposites, with the object of enhancing mechanical and tribological properties, as well as biocompatibility. However, challenges remain in achieving uniform dispersion and robust interfacial interactions between BaTiO_3 particles and the UHMWPE matrix. To take full advantage of the reinforcements, the aforementioned factors must be viewed as essential. In the present study, UHMWPE/ BaTiO_3 nanocomposites were synthesised with systematically varied concentrations of BaTiO_3 to identify the optimal filler content. Upon determining the most effective composition, a subsequent phase of the investigation was to surface-functionalise BaTiO_3 nanoparticles utilising a silane-based coupling agent to enhance the dispersion of the nanoparticles, thereby further improving the overall performance of the nanocomposite [2]. This two-phase approach aims to develop a robust nanocomposite system for prospective load-bearing applications. The main criterion of effectiveness of composites examined in this article was their tribological performance during dry sliding against 316L and Co-Cr-Mo alloy counter-bodies.

2. Materials and methods

For this work, UHMWPE powder with a molecular weight of approximately 5.0×10^6 g/mol, a density of 0.93 g/cm³ was used as a matrix. Tetragonal barium titanate with a mean size of 280 nm was used as a nanofiller. Isopropanol was employed as a dispersant to form colloidal formations of materials. APTES [(3-Aminopropyl)triethoxysilane] was used as a surface functionalising agent.

2.1 Sample fabrication

Polymer composites of UHMWPE/ BaTiO_3 were fabricated at five different filler weight percentages, up to 10 wt%. The UHMWPE and BaTiO_3 powders were dispersed in isopropanol, ultrasonicated, and mixed. The mixture was then mechanically stirred and dried in an oven to eliminate residual moisture. The resulting powder was moulded into thin sheets using hot compression moulding. The synthesised composites are named NEAT (pure UHMWPE), C2.5, C5, C7.5, and C10. Additionally, for the C5 composite, APTES was employed for surface functionalisation of BaTiO_3 via a reflux reaction. The processed powder was subjected to the same method, and the sample was designated as C5m.

2.2 Composite Characterisation

Tribological testing was conducted using the pin-on-disc tribometer. Two different counter-body materials were tested, namely Co-Cr-Mo alloy as per ISO 5832-4, and 316L stainless steel. Co-Cr-Mo counter-bodies were in the form of pins with a radius of 3 mm, whereas 316L was in the form of 6 mm balls.

A normal load of 1 N was applied during the test. Linear sliding speed of 50 mm/s, and number of laps 20000 were used for all tests. In each configuration, tests were conducted twice.

The wear of the counter body surface and the wear track on the planar sample were analysed using a digital microscope Olympus DSX1000 after the test. For all tested combinations specific wear rate k was calculated from the volume of the wear track, using the normal load and, known sliding distance. The volume of the wear track was calculated by multiplying the area of the wear track cross-section, measured by Sensofar S neox optical profilometer, by its length.

Measurement of the hardness of the materials was rendered by the Vickers hardness tester for neat sample and composites C5 and C5m (Struers Duramin 40AC3) according to ISO 6507 standards.

Bioactivity tests were performed on C5m by immersing the composites in simulated body fluid (SBF) in accordance with ISO 23317:2014. Samples were kept in SBF for 21 days at a temperature of 36.5 °C. Inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (OES-ICP) Spectro ARCOS (Spectro, Germany) was used to determine the Ca and P concentrations of the SBF solution before and after the test. The surface of the samples was further observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) on a JEOL JSM-7600F electron microscope.

3. Results and Discussion

Results of tribological testing of unmodified composites UHMWPE/BaTiO₃ against Co-Cr-Mo counter-body are presented in Figure 1 and can be summarised as follows. The lowest friction was achieved on the sample with 7.5 % BaTiO₃ and was around 0.1. All composites exhibited significantly lower COF than neat UHMWPE. COF of neat polymer was around 0.16, which is comparable with results obtained in literature for similar tests [5]. The specific wear rate of all samples is around 5×10^{-6} mm³/Nm regardless of composition.

During dry sliding, polymer transfer film forms on the surface of pins. This film can be easily removed after a test. Co-Cr-Mo pins exhibit clear scratches caused by contact. The wear of pins didn't observably increase with the amount of filler in composites. In regard to wear as well as friction, it is important to note that Co-Cr-Mo pins have very low surface roughness ($S_a = 16 \pm 1$ nm), which leads to lower wear and higher COF due to a higher actual contact area [6–8]. Wear of pins, however, changes this, as it significantly increases roughness, which contributes to abrasive wear of samples.

The coefficient of friction during tests with 316L balls fell in the range of 0.1 to 0.14, without any correlation with the amount of fillers, as visible in Figure 2. The lowest COF was measured on samples C5 and C7.5. The specific wear rate of all samples is around 7×10^{-6} mm³/Nm, and it isn't possible to distinguish between them due to statistical variations.

Figure 1. a) coefficient of friction, b) specific wear rate for dry sliding with Co-Cr-Mo pins

The high roughness of used balls ($S_a = 85 \pm 8 \text{ nm}$) contributes to an increase in abrasive wear. This leads to a higher wear rate in comparison with Co-Cr-Mo. The surface of 316L balls shows visible wear scratches after the test. Based on these tests and tests with Co-Cr-Mo, it can be concluded that samples cause significant wear of relatively soft metal counter-bodies under dry sliding conditions. This wear is observable regardless of BaTiO_3 content and is present after the test with neat UHMWPE.

Figure 2. a) coefficient of friction, b) specific wear rate for dry sliding with 316L balls

For evaluation of the influence of surface activation, the sample C5 was chosen as it demonstrated improved tribological properties in both cases and the surface activation of BaTiO_3 leads to significant changes in tribological performance of composites. The results for both tested combinations are presented in Figure 3. The main difference observed in both testing against 316L and Co-Cr-Mo was a significant reduction in specific wear rate. In the case of the 316L counter-body, this reduction was 44 % and in the case of Co-Cr-Mo, only 23 %. This can be explained by the higher surface roughness of 316L, which leads to higher abrasive wear. Activation improved adhesion between hard particles of filler and polymer matrix and improved the abrasion resistance of the composite. In the case of Co-Cr-Mo, adhesion and fatigue constitute most of the wear, resulting in smaller improvements.

Figure 3. a) specific wear rate against 316L, b) specific wear rate against Co-Cr-Mo, c) coefficient of friction against 316L, d) coefficient of friction against Co-Cr-Mo

The friction coefficient of the modified composite didn't experience any such improvement. In case of sliding against Co-Cr-Mo, it is virtually identical to that of unmodified composites. During tests with the 316L ball, it is even higher and roughly equal to that of neat PE.

Addition of filler leads to an increase in the hardness of the tested samples, as visible in Figure 4. Surface activation increases hardness further. This is likely one of the underlying factors behind the improvement in wear resistance of sample C5m. Higher hardness, on the other hand, leads to higher shear strength, which results in as high or higher COF in comparison with sample C5 [9].

Figure 4. Vickers Hardness of neat PE and composite C5 and composite C5m with activated BaTiO₃

Results of the analysis of Ca and P concentration are listed in Figure 5. As is visible, there isn't any distinctive correlation between time and the concentration of observed elements. The fact that the SBF without sample have a lower concentration than one with composites for 7 and 14 days is probably due to a small amount of precipitation onto used bottles and represents a variation of measurement. Likewise, the SEM analysis didn't reveal any presence of hydroxyapatite on the samples. These results indicate that the concentration of filler wasn't sufficient to allow the growth of hydroxyapatite on otherwise inert PE samples.

Figure 5. Ca and P concentration of sample C5m after testing in SBF for 0-21 days

4. Conclusion

UHMWPE/BaTiO₃ nanocomposites were prepared by hot compression molding. Based on the testing presented in this paper, the following conclusion can be reached:

- Addition of BaTiO₃ can lead to improvement of the coefficient of friction of UHMWPE during dry sliding with 316L and Co-Cr-Mo. However, it doesn't improve the specific wear rate to a statistically significant degree.
- Surface modification of BaTiO₃ with APTES leads to an increase in the hardness of composites. This significantly improves wear resistance during dry sliding. It doesn't lead to any improvement of the coefficient of friction and can in fact lead to higher COF.
- During exposure of the composite to SBF, no detectable growth of hydroxyapatite was observed. The tested concentration of BaTiO₃ isn't high enough to enable such growth.

The results demonstrate that the properties of UHMWPE/BaTiO₃ nanocomposites are significantly improved by surface activation. This predisposes such composites as attractive materials for load-bearing implant applications. Further examination of biocompatibility, mechanical properties, as well as the influence of the environment on the tribological properties of nanocomposites is needed.

Data available

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in the repository ZENODO at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16365964>

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